

**MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION BETWEEN
PSYCHOSOCIAL HAZARDS AND RETENTION IN PRIVATE
HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN CALAMBA CITY**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 6

Pages: 736-746

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2295

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13626198

Manuscript Accepted: 08-07-2024

Mediating Effect of Employee Satisfaction Between Psychosocial Hazards and Retention in Private Higher Education Institutions in Calamba City

Judy Ann C. Cerillo*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The research was conducted to determine if there was a mediating effect of employee satisfaction between psychosocial hazards and retention intention among Private Higher Education Institutions (PHEI) employees. With the aid of G*power, a sample size of 120 employees of selected PHEIs in Calamba City were included through a multistage sampling technique. The Job Descriptive Index was adopted to measure employee satisfaction and retention, and the Job-Demands-Control questionnaire (CVR = 1.00) (Cronbach's $\alpha = .767$) was adapted to measure psychosocial hazards. Employing mediation analysis, data were gathered and analyzed using regression and the Sobel test. It was revealed that among PHEI employees, the level of psychosocial hazards was very low, and the level of employee satisfaction and retention was high. It was also revealed that psychosocial hazards had a significant impact on employee satisfaction ($B = 2.281, p < .001$), wherein psychosocial hazards accounted for 40.4% of the variance in employee satisfaction, employee satisfaction had a significant impact on retention level ($B = -.996, p < .001$) wherein, employee satisfaction accounted 63.9% of the variance in retention, and psychosocial hazards had significant impact with retention level ($B = .691, p < .001$) wherein, psychosocial hazards accounted 39.4% of the variance in retention. Furthermore, employee satisfaction carried a significant effect on the relationship between psychosocial hazards and retention of PHEI employees which meant that the relationship between psychosocial hazards and retention is mediated by employee satisfaction. Lastly, an action plan was proposed intended to be used by the Human Resource Department of each PHEI.

Keywords: *employee satisfaction, psychosocial hazards, retention, mediation*

Introduction

Psychology has been introduced to human resource management to promote an increase in organizational diversity across businesses and with the utilization of psychological research guiding the development of more inclusive recruiting and training practices. Human resource primary functions include planning, recruitment and selection, performance management, learning and development, career planning, performance evaluation, risks and compliance, employee participation and communication, health safety, and personal well-being.

Stankich (2021) mentioned that HR professionals had a dual responsibility in focusing on employees and processes. In Eastern countries, they tended to value employees over processes. Eastern businesses frequently provided their workers with HR policies that capitalized on cultural traits that supported HR management. Such strategies that prioritized loyalty, hospitality, and long-term employer-employee relationships benefited greatly from the HR practices focused on training development and retention. Different from the East, Western leaders fostered a bottom-line viewpoint by assisting people in achieving success. They helped their employees grow by providing pertinent feedback during the performance management process employing a no-nonsense approach. However, the role of HR in global corporations was to uphold and advance company standards in a manner that was appropriate for employees from other countries. Respecting the individual struck a balance in honoring the collective.

As it was, Sprout's Quiet Quitting Report (as cited in Vega, 2023) mentioned that across the globe only 21% of workers were engaged in their jobs. In the Philippines, there was an average score of 4.30 over 5 which meant a high overall employee engagement. Fifty-three percent (53%) of workers chose to quit their jobs because of dissatisfaction with their pay. Given that 80% of workers indicated that they would be likely to stay with current companies if they were offered better benefits and pay, this highlighted the significance of firms placing a high priority on employee engagement. Satisfied employees were less inclined to seek new employment alternatives which could lead to higher employee retention. Once there was a sustained high percentage of employee retention, the costs of hiring and training new employees could be reduced.

Moreover, Desiderio (2023) stated that in October 2022 a survey conducted on 800 office employees working in the Philippines, Malaysia, Singapore, Indonesia, Vietnam, and Thailand, showed the motivations and perceptions behind quiet-quitting. According to the report, 23% of the Filipino employees surveyed began quietly quitting their jobs a long time ago, while 37% started doing so more recently. The region's top reasons included: taking care of mental health (48%), prioritizing work-life balance (42%), lacking prospects for career advancement or salary increase (40%), and inadequate pay (40%).

Similarly, Henson (2023) emphasized that the majority of employers understand how important it is to keep the workplace safe and healthy for the employees. Sometimes the more subtle and complicated health and safety problems associated with the workplace arose from psychosocial hazards. In a nutshell, a psychosocial hazard was anything that had the potential to cause psychological injury. These might range from extremely typical workplace problems like excessive workloads to more serious risks like harassment or excessive

exposure to traumatic materials or situations. Psychosocial safety issues can be more difficult to recognize and address than physical ones. Executive teams and people leaders in the workplace needed to have an honest discussion about mental health.

Furthermore, about mental health as a reason for low employee retention, the Department of Labor in Employment (2020), stated Guidelines for the Implementation of Mental Health Workplace Policies and Programs for the Private Sector required all businesses to create a Mental Health Workplace Policy and Program to increase awareness, combat stigma and prejudice, helped employees who may be with or at risk for mental health issues and make access to mental health services easier.

In this research, psychosocial hazards are risks that can cause psychological harm at work, such as psychological demand, decision latitude, decision authority, and social support. Employee satisfaction refers to the attitude of an employee toward their job. Employee retention refers to the process in which employees are encouraged to stay in the organization.

Finally, the purpose of this study was to ascertain whether or not satisfaction acted as a mediator between the two variables. As a practitioner working in the field, it was crucial in our role to identify the potential risks and in what aspects employees became more satisfied to ensure a productive and healthy working environment. Learning these aspects may improve the mental health of the employees and also help the success and growth of the institution. This research was also beneficial for the education institutions as a reference on how they could improve their retention rate from the impact of psychosocial hazards.

Research Questions

This research determined the significant impact of the level of employee satisfaction on the relationship between psychosocial hazards and retention of Private Higher Education Institutions (PHEIs) employees. Specifically, the research answered the following:

1. What is the level of psychosocial hazards as assessed by PHEI employees in Calamba City?
2. What is the employee satisfaction level among PHEI employees?
3. What is the retention level among PHEI employees?
4. Does psychosocial hazard level in PHEI employees significantly impact employee satisfaction level?
5. Does employee satisfaction level in PHEI employees significantly impact retention level?
6. Does psychosocial hazards level in PHEI employees significantly impact retention level?
7. Does employee satisfaction mediate the relationship between psychosocial hazards and retention?
8. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

Kharbach (2018, as cited in Creswell & Creswell, 2024) stated that quantitative research was a method for testing objective theories by the examination of the relationship among variables. Through the utilization of instruments, these variables were measured, and numbered data were analyzed through the use of statistical procedures. In this research, the theory was analyzed, data was gathered through instruments, and was treated with statistical procedures to either support or contradict the hypotheses.

Specifically, this research utilized mediation analysis. As mentioned in Hung (2020), mediation analysis is the statistical approach utilized to investigate hypotheses regarding how a potential independent variable (X) exerts its effect on a dependent variable (Y). This method was used in this research to examine if employee satisfaction has a mediating effect between the relationship of psychosocial hazards and the retention of the PHEIs employees.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were Private Higher Education Institutions employees in Calamba City, Laguna who were employed for at least six (6) months regardless of gender, age, designation, and employment status. The number of respondents per school differs as random sampling techniques were employed in this research. The selected schools from three clusters were: Laguna College of Business and Arts, Saint Benilde International School, and Institution A (code name was used to ensure the anonymity of the school as they preferred). The number of respondents per school was shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

<i>Private Higher Educational Institution</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>
Laguna College of Business and Arts	50
Saint Benilde Integrated School – Calamba	30
“PHEI A”	40
Total	120

Instrument

This research utilized an adapted and adopted research instrument that answered the specific objectives of this study.

First, the Swedish Job-Control-Demand Support Questionnaire (JCDSQ) was developed as a shortened and modified version of the Job Control Questionnaire (JCQ). It was a representative concept in examining the interaction between the psychosocial work environment and occupational stress responses. It focused on job task profiles and measures the following 3 uncorrelated components: psychological demands (PD), decision latitude (DL), and social support (SS). In this research, only the social support (SS) indicators were adopted and the psychological demands (PD) and the decision latitude (DL) were modified and validated by the experts.

Lastly, to measure the level of employee satisfaction and retention intention, the Job Descriptive Index (Biaison, 2020) was utilized. It was a five-subscale measure of employee job satisfaction. The five facets were Compensation, Job-content, Promotion, Supervisor, Colleagues, and Retention. It is a 32-item instrument rated by the respondents on a 5-point Likert scale format response (i.e., Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neither Agree nor Disagree, Agree, and Strongly Agree).

Procedure

For the data gathering procedure, first, a letter of inquiry was sent via email and in hardcopy to each selected respective PHEIs asking permission to survey their institution. The letter discussed the research title, rationale, research objectives, the qualifications and number of respondents needed, privacy and confidentiality, and a copy of the questionnaire. PHEI also asked if they wanted to be mentioned or conceal their institution's name in this research if they opted to.

Second, after approval of the PHEI, the dissemination of the survey questionnaire was then conducted. The research instrument was made in two ways: an electronic and a hard copy. Before answering, respondents were given informed consent to discuss the nature and objectives of the research. After agreeing to the informed consent and ethical considerations, the survey questionnaire was then disseminated either through Google Forms or hard copy.

Third, the respondents answered the two (2) sets of questions (adapted JCDSQ and JDI). The outputs from the Google form were readily tallied and can be generated online while the outputs from hard copy were manually tallied. All outputs were consolidated and sent to the statistician for the statistical treatment of data.

Data Analysis

The following were the statistical treatments that were applied to address the specific objectives of the study. These were (1) descriptive statistics, (2) regression analysis, and (3) Sobel test technique.

For the first, second, and third objectives of the study, the research utilized descriptive statistics, particularly using means, frequency tables, and percentages, to treat the data gathered in determining the PHEIs employees' level of psychosocial hazards, satisfaction, and retention, respectively.

To answer the fourth, fifth, and sixth objectives, this research utilized linear regression. Gravetter et al. (2020) mentioned that for prediction, regression is defined using the relationship between two or more variables, therefore, this is used to determine if the three variables that were used in the study singly or in combination significantly impact each other and if the mediating variable mediated the relationship between the independent and dependent variable.

Finally, this research utilized the Sobel Test. Preacher et al. (2020) emphasized that the Sobel Test examines whether the inclusion of a mediator (M) in the regression analysis considerably influences the effect of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y).

Ethical Considerations

To guarantee that research was carried out ethically and about the rights and welfare of the respondents, ethical considerations were addressed in this study.

Informed consent was made sure to be given and discussed with the respondents clarifying the respondent's role, nature of the study, purpose of the study, duration of the study, and the respondent's right to withdraw from participation at any point of the conduct of research. Privacy, confidentiality, and anonymity were also considered in this study to protect and respect the respondent's autonomy and dignity in answering the survey questionnaire. Respondents had the right to control their personal information to be disclosed in the course of gathering information. This aimed to protect the identity of the respondent's sensitive information to be collected during the research. The data handling process was one of the main considerations in this research concerning the integrity of data and critically ensuring the security and confidentiality to prevent disclosure of any information from the respondents to any unauthorized person. It also strictly secured the retention or preservation of the data as it would be kept only within the educational institution of the researcher. Adhering to these ethical considerations ensured the rights and wellbeing of the respondents while contributing to this study.

Furthermore, these ethical considerations guarantee that this research was performed responsibly and ethically by taking and upholding the importance of informed consent, confidentiality, privacy and anonymity, and data handling. This promoted aspects that were fundamental to collaborative work including trust, accountability, respect, and honesty between the respondents and the researcher.

Results and Discussion

This section presents analyses, significant findings, and discussions that answer the specific objectives of the study.

Problem Number 1. What is the level of psychosocial hazards as assessed by PHEI employees in Calamba City?

Table 1. *Level of Psychosocial Hazards as assessed by PHEI Employees in Calamba City*

Indicators in terms of Psychosocial Hazards	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. I need to work quickly to meet the deadlines.	3.60	VL	11
2. I need to put intensive concentration at work.	3.58	VL	13
3. I need to give more than a hundred percent of my effort.	3.64	VL	9.5
4. I have enough time to complete my tasks.	3.58	VL	13
5. I ask my colleagues/superiors on how to perform contradicting tasks	3.68	VL	8
6. I learn new things through my work	3.69	VL	7
7. I need to enhance my competencies to perform my work	3.64	VL	9.5
8. I need to be creative and inventive in my work.	3.58	VL	13
9. I need to repeat the same tasks over and over again.	3.36	VL	17
10. I can influence decisions on how to complete my tasks.	3.54	VL	15
11. I can influence decisions about the nature of my work.	3.43	VL	16
12. There is a calm and comfortable atmosphere in my workplace.	3.75	VL	5
13. Everyone in my workplace gets on well with each other.	3.79	VL	3
14. My colleagues support me.	3.78	VL	4
15. The people around me show some understanding when I am not feeling well at my best.	3.81	VL	2
16. I have a good relationship with my superiors.	3.74	VL	6
17. I have a good time working with my colleagues.	3.83	VL	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.65	VL	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00, Every time/Very Low (VL); 2.50 – 3.24, Often/Low (L); 1.75 – 2.49, Rarely/High (H); 1.00 – 1.74, Never/Very High (VH)

Psychosocial Hazards was Very Low Psychosocial Hazards (3.65) as to the level of psychosocial hazards as assessed by PHEI employees in Calamba City. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Every time or Very Low Psychosocial Hazards. Furthermore, the indicator “I have a good time working with my colleagues” had the highest computed mean of 3.83 meanwhile, the indicator “I need to repeat the same tasks over and over again” had the lowest computed mean of 3.36.

Psychosocial hazards have the potential to cause harm to an individual's mental health or wellbeing. Exposure to this risk may have a negative effect on the physical and mental health of employees. The level of psychosocial hazards in the workplace of PHEIs is very low because they are having a good time working with their colleagues. These strong relationships may imply a healthy and stress-free working environment that builds team cohesion and collaboration. This might also be because these institutions provide countless training and support for their employees in developing of skills and knowledge employees need for the job. PHEIs foster a positive work culture where superiors support their subordinates and vice versa. Moreover, the physical working conditions of the job are considered and given importance and employees might have freedom in execution over the job design or workload assigned to them. Lastly, they see repetitive tasks as a psychosocial hazard however it yielded the lowest computed mean. This may imply that the respondents may experience repeating the same tasks but with a very low frequency.

According to Unmind and Partner (2023), having insufficient procedures in place was both expensive and careless, as managing psychological health and safety in the workplace was not only a top priority but also a legal need. A factor influencing mental health outcomes was exposure to psychosocial risks. Studies indicated that there was a significant correlation between mental health concerns and limited social support, high job pressure, and role stress. Therefore, the lower the psychosocial hazards, the higher the chance of having a stable mental health of employees.

Ede et al. (2022) mentioned that specialists in the workplace, especially educators, should create workable treatments that would aid in lowering workplace deviation among workers from various walks of life. This calls for their inclusion in policy development and implementation for rural communities and elsewhere. Thus, this action may promote sustainability in providing a healthy working environment and conditions in the workplace. Problem Number 2. What is the employee satisfaction level of PHEI employees?

Employee Satisfaction was High (3.96) as to the employee satisfaction level in PHEI employees. The indicator “I am satisfied at work because I and my colleagues get along with each other” had the highest computed mean of 4.49 verbally interpreted as Very High meanwhile, the indicator “I am satisfied because there is adequate opportunity for periodic changes in duties” had the lowest computed

mean of 3.65 verbally interpreted as High.

Based on the result, employees in PHEI have high employee satisfaction which may indicate that they are happy, involved, and fulfilled in their positions as well as in the institution overall. It might be because they are contented with the monetary value they receive in the institutions. They are satisfied with the content of their job and they are being supervised accordingly by their superiors. Furthermore, it may also imply a positive work culture where that might be characterized by trust, collaboration, and mutual respect. Lastly, even though the respondents are experiencing repetitive tasks, there is still an adequate opportunity for periodic changes in duty. It means that they can get tasks that are new to them and not routine. This is why it yielded the least indicative of the respondent's employee satisfaction.

Table 2. *Employee Satisfaction Level in PHEI Employees*

Indicators in terms of Employee Satisfaction		\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1.	I am satisfied with the salary that I receive from my work.	3.77	H	18.5
2.	I am satisfied with the benefits that I receive from work (Health Insurance, vacation I and sick leaves.)	3.66	H	26
3.	I am paid fairly with the work I contribute to my company.	3.72	H	23
4.	I am satisfied at work because there are bonuses/rewards given for excellent performance.	3.71	H	24
5.	I am satisfied with the salary that I receive from my company.	3.76	H	20
6.	I am satisfied of the number of hours that I work every month.	4.02	H	11.5
7.	I am satisfied with the work that I am doing in my company.	4.05	H	10
8.	I am satisfied because there is a degree of independence associated with my work roles.	3.87	H	15
9.	I am satisfied at work because I was recognized for the good work accomplished.	3.97	H	13
10.	I am satisfied because there is adequate opportunity for periodic changes in duties.	3.65	H	27
11.	I am satisfied with my work because there are opportunities for promotion	3.69	H	25
12.	I am satisfied with my work because there is support for additional training.	3.81	H	16.5
13.	I am satisfied with my work because there is an opportunity to learn new skills.	3.96	H	14
14.	I am satisfied at work because there is an ability to utilize my skills and talents.	4.02	H	11.5
15.	I am satisfied at work because I can be promoted base on my work performance.	3.75	H	21
16.	I am satisfied at work because I can be promoted base on my educational qualification.	3.81	H	16.5
17.	I am satisfied at work because I am always treated fairly by my supervisor.	4.13	H	8
18.	I am satisfied because my supervisor encourages us to set high goals.	4.17	H	6
19.	I am satisfied because my supervisor does a good job sharing information.	4.10	H	9
20.	I am satisfied because I feel comfortable discussing problems with my supervisor.	3.73	H	22
21.	I am satisfied because my supervisor treats me with respect.	4.31	VH	3.5
22.	I am satisfied because I receive useful and constructive feedback from my direct supervisor.	4.31	VH	3.5
23.	I am satisfied at work because I and my colleagues get along with each other.	4.49	VH	1
24.	I am satisfied at work because everyone works together to solve problems and meet operational goals.	4.14	H	7
25.	I am satisfied at work because I am treated with the way other co-workers treat me on the job.	4.22	VH	5
26.	I am satisfied at work because my co-workers have the same workload as I have	3.77	H	18.5
27.	I am satisfied at work because I and my colleagues get along with each other.	4.36	VH	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT		3.96	H	

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00, Strongly Agree/Very High (VH); 3.40 – 4.19, Agree/High (H); 2.60 – 3.39, Neither Agree nor Disagree/Slightly High (SH); 1.80 – 2.59, Disagree/Low (L); 1.00 – 1.79, Strongly Disagree/Very Low (VL)

To support the conclusion above, Jahan et al. (2023) stated that a happy and content employee improves the business or organization by reducing employee turnover, boosting productivity, raising customer satisfaction, and encouraging loyalty. Additionally, content employees who leave the organization and firm are more likely to assist in passing along their knowledge and skills to others since they take into account both the welfare of the organization and the coworkers being left behind.

Furthermore, Bella (2023) claimed in her study that a collaborative work environment, positive co-worker relationships, and supportive supervisor-subordinate relationships significantly increase employee satisfaction. By fostering an environment in the workplace where staff members can develop close bonds with their coworkers and managers. Companies should place a high priority on encouraging open dialogue, trust, and teamwork between employees. Implementing tactics that encourage a culture of trust, open communication, and teamwork can be beneficial for organizations.

Problem Number 3. What is the retention level of PHEI employees?

Retention was High (3.79) as to the retention level of PHEI employees. All indicators were verbally interpreted as High. The indicator "I want to stay with my company because the job description matches my skills, experience, and education" had the highest computed

mean of 3.85 meanwhile, the indicator “I want to stay with my company because there are retirement benefits” had the lowest computed mean of 3.73.

Table 3. Retention Level in PHEI Employees

Indicators in terms of Retention Level	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. I want to stay with my company because there is career advancement for me.	3.81	H	2
2. I want to stay with my company because there are retirement benefits.	3.73	H	5
3. I want to stay in my company because there would be a salary increase upon regularization.	3.78	H	3.5
4. I want to stay with my company because the job description matches my skills, experience, and education.	3.85	H	1
5. I want to stay with my company because there is career advancement for me.	3.78	H	3.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.79	H	

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00, Strongly Agree/Very High (VH); 3.40 – 4.19, Agree/High (H); 2.60 – 3.39, Neither Agree nor Disagree/Slightly High (SH); 1.80 – 2.59, Disagree/Low (L); 1.00 – 1.79, Strongly Disagree/Very Low (VL)

As to the results above, the retention level of PHEI employees was high which may imply that a significant number of employees in the institutions were intended to stay in the company for an anticipated future because they are well-suited to their roles. Since they work with their expertise, there is a big chance of career advancement as they show mastery in their positions. It showed how the employees were willing and committed to sticking with the company in their existing positions. It might be because the institutions have an established process in terms of selection of the right employees in a position and there is a fit pay structure and career advancement program existing in the institution. The PHEI recognized the skills, experience, and education of its employees. A high level of retention may indicate a reduction in turnover rates, a positive work environment, and employee engagement. Employees who are well-fitted to their designations can efficiently and effectively perform, leading to increased productivity.

As mentioned by Sorn (2023), the success of a company depends on its ability to retain qualified and talented workers since doing so can increase productivity, improve performance, and lower turnover costs. Offering competitive pay and benefits, providing opportunities for professional advancement, maintaining a nice work environment, and recognizing and rewarding employee accomplishments are some frequent employee retention techniques. Employee retention was found to be significantly influenced by motivation.

Similarly, Chand (2023) mentioned that in today's competitive and quickly changing business world, it has become essential for firms to prosper, grow, and achieve to retain valuable people. Employee retention decisions can be influenced by a variety of elements, including a leader's style, pay, and benefits, learning opportunities, and employee satisfaction. Employees who find their job to be a great match are most likely to stay in the company they are in. They also feel fulfilled if their job aligns with their qualifications which increases their satisfaction and morale as an employee.

Problem Number 4. Does psychosocial hazard level in PHEI employees significantly impact employee satisfaction level?

Table 4. Regression Analysis on the Impact of Psychosocial Hazard Level in PHEI Employees on Employee Satisfaction Level

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta					
(Constant)	2.281	.351			6.497	.000		
Psychosocial Hazard Level	.460	.096	.404		4.795	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION LEVEL; R-Square = .404; F-value = 22.990; Adjusted R-Square = .163; Significance = .000

The psychological hazard level in PHEI employees significantly impacted the Employee Satisfaction level. The probability value of .000 was less than the level of significance at .05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

The results of the study reveal that the Psychosocial Hazard level in PHEI Employees significantly impacts the Employee Satisfaction Level by 40.4%. Hence, it is indeed important for the PHEIs to make an effort to mitigate these psychosocial hazards in the workplace. Exposure to psychosocial hazards may lead to anxiety which affects mental health negatively. Employees who experience constant stress may feel stressed and dissatisfied in their jobs. Very low psychosocial hazards may enhance overall employee satisfaction because

if the employees are supported, their level of morale may be boosted, leading to a positive work environment.

Moreover, since the respondents scored very low in the level of psychosocial hazards because they have a strong working relationship with colleagues, superiors, and subordinates, this significantly impacted their employee satisfaction as for them, satisfaction is the camaraderie, collaborative effort from the team, strong social support, and the positive working environment. Simply, if the respondents have a hostile working environment and do not promote any support from their heads or co-workers, the level of employee satisfaction tends to score low. Employees who are dissatisfied in their jobs are those who have conflicts within their departments or the organization they working in.

To support this Rivera-Rojas et al. (2021) stated in their study that there is an association between the perception of psychosocial risk and employee satisfaction, demonstrating that the more exposed to psychosocial risks, the more dissatisfied the oncology workers are, which affects work environments.

Additionally, Wulandari et al. (2020) mentioned that psychosocial hazards and employee satisfaction were significantly and negatively correlated among academic and non-academic personnel. Significant predictors of decreased job satisfaction included variables including excessive workload, little job control, position uncertainty, and interpersonal problems. The results highlight the significance of mitigating psychosocial dangers in the workplace to improve worker satisfaction and overall well-being. Thus, this emphasized the need for the companies to initiate interventions that aimed to lessen these hazards to improve the overall employee satisfaction among employees.

Problem Number 5. Does employee satisfaction level in PHEI employees significantly impact retention level?

Table 5. *Regression Analysis on the Impact of Employee Satisfaction Level in PHEI Employees on Retention Level*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta					
(Constant)	-0.996	.532			-1.873	.064		
Employee Satisfaction Level	1.209	.134	.639		9.022	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Dependent Variable: RETENTION LEVEL: R-Square = .639; F-value = 81.390; Adjusted R-Square = .408; Significance = .000

The employee satisfaction level in PHEI employees significantly impacted retention level. The probability value of .000 was less than the level of significance at .05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

The results of the study revealed that Employee Satisfaction level in PHEI Employees significantly impacts Retention level by 63.9%. This would imply that the more satisfied the respondents, the higher the level of retention intention would be. For instance, if an employee feels comfortable in expressing her ideas and opinions within his/her team, and this employee has a right fit in doing his/her role in the organization where the qualifications match his/her skills, this employee has a high level of satisfaction in her work that could lead to an intention to stay in the organization for a longer time. On the contrary, if an employee experiences judgment, bias, and hostility in his/her work, there is a high chance of leaving the institution resulting in a high turnover rate meaning another cost to the company. This shows how employee satisfaction significantly impacts retention levels. The above result supported by Singh (2019, as cited in Hausknecht et al., 2019) claimed that the major reason for retention was employee satisfaction. Also, as mentioned in Terera et al. (2019) it was found that there is a strong relationship between employee retention and employee satisfaction providing companies information on how to retain their employees.

Strategies on how to retain employees may differ from companies. Solo (2021) mentioned that the institution's strategies for keeping employees included strengthening orientation roles and programs for newly hired staff, promoting work-life balance, matching employees with the right jobs and qualifications, providing a supportive work environment, fostering employee appreciation and value, offering competitive salaries and benefits, encouraging and strengthening workplace teamwork, and stepping up the recruitment and selection process.

Problem Number 6. Does psychosocial hazard level in PHEI employees significantly impact retention level?

The psychosocial hazard level in PHEI employees significantly impacted the retention level. The probability value of .000 was less than the level of significance at .05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

The Psychosocial Hazards level in PHEI Employees significantly impacts the Retention level by 39.4%. Low levels of psychosocial hazards significantly impact retention leading to a high level. Employees who experience a fun, and lighter office culture could result in a high level of employee retention. Employees tend to stay in the institutions if they have experienced a healthy work climate, support

each other, and collaborate to achieve organizational success. Hence, the intention of employees to stay in the institution is associated with the risks present in the workplace which may affect their physical and mental health.

Table 6. *Regression Analysis on the Impact of Psychological Hazard Level in PHEI Employees on Retention Level*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta					
(Constant)	.691	.667			1.036	.302		
Psychological Hazard Level	.850	.183	.394		4.655	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Dependent Variable: RETENTION LEVEL; R-Square = .394; F-value = 21.672; Adjusted R-Square = .155; Significance = .000

Xue et al. (2022) reiterated that workers have no desire to work in a setting that does not support mental health. There was a substantial chance of psychological exhaustion. According to the literature, the psychological effects made it possible for workplace features to be a major cause of mental imbalances, which prevented the person from being able to handle the demands of the job. Supervisors expected their employees to handle a heavy workload to relieve workplace pressure, which lowered employee well-being and increases the likelihood of higher turnover intention.

Problem Number 7. Does employee satisfaction mediate the relationship between psychosocial hazards and retention?

Table 7. *Test of Mediation of Employee Satisfaction to Psychosocial Hazards and Retention*

Regression	t value	Sobel Test Test Statistics	p-value	Decisions	Remarks
Psychosocial Hazards and Employee Satisfaction	4.795	3.15533947	0.0016031	Reject Ho	Significant
Employee Satisfaction and Retention	9.022				

Mediator: Employee Satisfaction; Critical Value = 1.96

Employee satisfaction carried a significant effect on the relationship between psychosocial hazards and retention of PHEI. Using the Sobel Test, the p-value of .000 was less than the level of significance at .05, and the null hypothesis was rejected.

Psychosocial hazards significantly impact employee retention by influencing the level of satisfaction of PHEI employees. PHEIs that effectively address psychosocial hazards and foster positive work conditions can enhance employee satisfaction which may lead to a higher level of retention. Conversely, if employees experience high levels of psychosocial hazards, the level of employee satisfaction tends to decrease which may result in high turnover rates or low levels of retention.

Paul (2023) supported that there was a positive relationship between employee satisfaction, retention, and psychosocial safety. These hazards impacted more than just the employee and the organization. Workers who merely collaborated as a team rather than managing personnel should be aware of these aspects and the way, they affected psychosocial safety could lead to behavior that was not as deliberate. Workers should concentrate on these, such as minimizing stress and conversing with team members and managers in the same language as their coworkers based on how they felt supported with knowledge from both the individual and organizational levels.

Problem Number 8. Based on the results of this study, what action plan may be proposed?

As an output, an action plan was proposed intended to use of Human Resource Department to serve as a guide in the implementation of job enrichment to reduce dealing with repetitive tasks; in rewarding employees through incentives and bonuses to increase employee satisfaction and boost their morale; in the discussion of overview of retirement benefits to make them aware on the security that awaits them when they get old with the institution; in providing free additional training to develop employee's skills and competencies; and outlining roadmap for career advancement to widen the professional network of employees.

First, the implementation of job enrichment is proposed to satisfy the result of this research wherein respondents experienced the same tasks again and again. To reduce repetitive tasks, job enrichment may be implemented by PHEI to provide opportunities for employees to handle different tasks to increase employee engagement and improve performance metrics. As the respondents see this routine task as a hazard, this action will mitigate the potential increase in psychosocial risks.

Second, regarding the least indicative factor of the respondents' employee satisfaction, rewarding employees through bonuses, incentives, and similar measures is proposed to improve employee satisfaction, boost performance, and minimize turnover rates. This action would further motivate PHEI employees to continuously perform productively and efficiently in their roles.

Moreover, providing additional training for free was also proposed, as this indicator scored low in employee satisfaction levels. This action would lead to developing employees' skills and competencies to perform their roles better. If an employee can perform well, they tend to become more efficient in their job, which may result in high satisfaction with their work outputs. This training could be conducted by the Human Resource personnel of the institution or outsourced to training centers.

Furthermore, a discussion of an overview of retirement benefits would make the employees aware of the things they might look forward to and influence their stay in the institution. This could be done through discussions in the new employee orientation for onboarding employees. So as early as the first day of their employment, they would learn about the retirement benefits of the institution, which would give them a sense of security and value. This, in turn, could lead to employees being happier and more content to stay for a longer time.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, several conclusions were drawn regarding the psychosocial hazards, employee satisfaction, and retention levels within Private Higher Education Institutions (PHEIs). The study revealed that the psychosocial hazard level, as assessed by PHEI employees, is very low. This is attributed to the institutions' efforts in fostering a healthy work culture that emphasizes social support and skill development training for their employees. A positive work environment is cultivated where there is mutual support between superiors and subordinates.

Additionally, the study found that employee satisfaction is high, indicating that employees are happy, engaged, and content in their roles as well as with the institution as a whole. Employees are satisfied with the job content and the supervision they receive. The high level of employee retention suggests that many employees intend to remain with the institution due to effective selection processes, a suitable pay structure, and career advancement opportunities.

The study also highlighted the significant influence of psychosocial hazard levels on employee satisfaction. In turn, employee satisfaction levels were found to significantly impact retention rates. Psychosocial hazards were also directly linked to retention levels, with employee satisfaction serving as a mediator in this relationship. This means that PHEIs that successfully address psychosocial hazards and create positive working conditions can enhance employee satisfaction, leading to higher retention rates. Conversely, high levels of psychosocial hazards can decrease employee satisfaction, potentially resulting in higher turnover rates or lower retention levels.

To maintain low levels of psychosocial hazards and improve employee satisfaction and retention, the study recommends that the Human Resource Department implement an action plan. This plan should include an annual Psychosocial Risk Assessment to identify and mitigate risks that could affect employees' physical and mental health. Training and seminars on stress management and work-life balance should be conducted regularly to prevent the escalation of psychosocial risks.

Furthermore, PHEIs are encouraged to provide opportunities for employees to move laterally within their departments and take on new responsibilities, thereby preventing dissatisfaction and boosting morale. Including information about retirement benefits in the New Employee Orientation can also give employees long-term incentives to stay with the institution. Moreover, fostering a positive work culture, improving compensation, training, and social support, and implementing mental health programs can further enhance employee satisfaction and retention.

The study suggests that future research could expand the scope to cover larger areas, such as provincial or regional levels, to represent broader populations across different schools. Additionally, similar studies could be conducted in public schools, as this study focused exclusively on private institutions.

References

- Abdi, F., Jahangiri, M., Kamalinia, M., Cousins, R., & Mokarami, H. (2023). Developing a model for predicting safety performance of nurses based on psychosocial safety climate and role of job demands and resources, job satisfaction, and emotional exhaustion as mediators. *BMC Psychology*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-023-01223-1>
- Alrawahi, S., Sellgren, S. F., Altouby, S., Alwahaibi, N., & Brommels, M. (2020). The application of Herzberg's two-factor theory of motivation to job satisfaction in clinical laboratories in Omani hospitals. *Heliyon*, 6(9), e04829. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04829>
- Basril, H. (2022). Literature review determination of employee satisfaction and performance: hygiene and motivator factors analysis. *Dinasti International Journal of Management Science*, 3, 976-984. <https://doi.org/10.31933/dijms.v3i5.1199>
- Belay, A., Gasheya, K., Engdaw, G., Guyasa, G., Tesfaye, A., Pisanti, R., Blettner, D., & Vallone, F. (2023). Work-related burnout among public secondary school teachers is significantly influenced by the psychosocial work factors: a cross-sectional study from

- Ethiopia. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1215421. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1215421>
- Bella, K. M. (2023). Exploring the impact of workplace relationships and employee job satisfaction. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Modern Science and Technology*, 2, 55-62. <https://doi.org/10.59828/ijrmst.v2i8.136>
- Biason, R. (2020). *The Effect Of Job Satisfaction On Employee Retention* [Thesis]. Salalah College of Technology.
- Chand, P. (2023). *Factors Determining Employee Retention of Development Banks In Nepal*.
- Creswell, J., & Creswell, J. D. (2024). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Cruz, D. D. (2023). Retention and job satisfaction among Filipino and offshore teachers: a comparative study. *AIDE Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 3, 139–153. <https://doi.org/10.56648/aide-irj.v3i1.59>
- Del Carmen Giménez-Espert, M., Prado-Gascó, V., & Soto-Rubio, A. (2020). Psychosocial risks, work engagement, and job satisfaction of nurses during COVID-19 pandemic. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.566896>
- Desiderio, L. (2023, January 5). 60% of workers quietly quitting, study reveals. *Philstar.com*.
- Devi, S., Vasudevan, A., Sagadavan, R., & Shiney (2023). Drivers of Employee Job Satisfaction During Pandemic in Manufacturing Industries. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8, e01018. <https://doi.org/10.26668/businessreview/2023.v8i10.1018>
- Ede, M. O., Aye, E. N., & Okeke, C. I. (2022). Assessment of psychosocial work hazards and workplace deviant behaviors of teachers in rural community-based schools. *Journal of Community Psychology*, 50. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcop.22848>
- Gravetter, F. J., Wallnau, L. B., Forzano, L. A. B., & Witnauer, J. E. (2020). *Essentials of statistics for the behavioral sciences*. Cengage Learning
- Henson, N. (2023). Impact of psychosocial hazards on the workplace: Actions employers can take to reduce the risks. *Lockton*. <https://global.lockton.com/au/en/news-insights/impact-of-psychosocial-hazards-on-the-workplace-actions-employers-can-take>
- Hmoud, M., Swaity, H., Anjass, E., & Aguaded-Ramírez, E. M. (2024). Rubric development and validation for assessing tasks' solving via AI chatbots. *Electronic Journal of e-Learning*, 22(6), 01–17. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ejel.22.6.3292>
- Hon, C., Sun, C., Way, K., Jimmieson, N., Xia, B., & Biggs, H. (2023). Psychosocial hazards affecting mental health in the construction industry: a qualitative study in Australia. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-07-2022-0617>
- Hung, M. T. (2020). *Teacher support and intrinsic motivation: The mediating roles of enjoyment, anxiety, and self-efficacy* [Thesis]. S.
- Jahan, G., Faridullah, L., Hafizullah, M. A. (2023). Exploring the Impact of Employee Satisfaction on Organizational Success: Evidence from Private Sector Organizations in Khost, Afghanistan. *Journal for Research in Applied Sciences and Biotechnology*, 2, 161-169. <https://doi.org/10.55544/jrasb.2.4.23>
- Journal ijmr.net.in (UGC Approved). (2020). *Employee Retention*. Kuk. https://www.academia.edu/43753833/EMPLOYEE_RETENTION
- Martin, T. (2021). *The Effects of Collaborative Leadership Practices on Employee Satisfaction Levels* [Dissertation]. Pepperdine University.
- McCombes, S. (2023, June 22). *Sampling Methods | Types, Techniques & Examples*. Scribbr.
- Paul, J. (2023). The Role of Psychological Safety on Employee Satisfaction and Retention in Healthcare delivery Settings: A Systematic literature review. *DigitalCommons@UNMC*. https://digitalcommons.unmc.edu/coph_slce/275?utm_source=digitalcommons.unmc.edu%2Fcoph_slce%2F275&utm_medium=PDF&utm_campaign=PDFCoverPages
- Portoghese, I., Galletta, M., Leiter, M. P., Finco, G., D'Aloja, E., & Campagna, M. (2020). Job Demand-Control-Support Latent Profiles and Their Relationships with Interpersonal Stressors, Job Burnout, and Intrinsic Work Motivation. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health/International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(24), 9430. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17249430>
- Preacher, K. J., & Geoffrey, L. (2020). Calculation for the Sobel Test: An Interactive Calculation Tool for Mediation Tests. Retrieved August 27, 2020 from <http://quantpsy.org/sobel/sobel.htm>
- Rivera-Rojas, F., Ceballos-Vásquez, P., & González-Palacios, Y. (2021). *Psychosocial Risks and Job Satisfaction: A Meaningful*

relationship for oncology workers*. <https://www.redalyc.org/journal/741/74168260004/html/>

Singh, D. (2019). A Literature Review on Employee Retention with Focus on Recent Trends. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science, Engineering, and Technology*, 425–431. <https://doi.org/10.32628/ijrst195463>

Solo, A. M. (2021). Exploring job satisfaction and employee retention in a private higher education institution (hei) in Zamboanga City. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=17088>

Sorn, M., Fienena, A., Ali, Y., Anis Ur Rehman, M., & Fu, G. (2023). The Effectiveness of Compensation in Maintaining Employee Retention. *OALib*, 10, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1110394>

Stankich, B. D. (2021, January 1). Comparison of HR Practices in Eastern and Western Countries. *Bizfluent*. <https://bizfluent.com/comparison-of-hr-practices-in-eastern-and-western-countries.html>

Unmind, & Partner, C. (2023, March 20). Why psychosocial hazards need to be top of mind for HR & WHS Leaders. *HR Leader*. <https://www.hrleader.com.au/business/23881-why-psychosocial-hazards-need-to-be-top-of-mind-for-hr-whs-leaders>

Vega, K. (2023, December 16). How to measure employee engagement to maximize retention and Productivity. *Sprout Solutions*. <https://sprout.ph/blog/how-to-measure-employee-engagement-to-maximize-retention/>

Wulandari, P. S., Priyatno, D., & Shinta, A. (2020). Psychosocial Hazards and Job Satisfaction: A Comparative Study among Academic and Non-Academic Employees. *Journal of Educational, Health, and Community Psychology*, 9

Xue, J., Wang, H., Chen, M., Ding, X., & Zhu, M. (2022). Signifying the relationship between psychological factors and turnover intention: the mediating role of Work-Related stress and moderating role of job satisfaction. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.847948>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Judy Ann C. Cerillo, RPh, MSP, CHRA

Laguna College of Business and Arts – Philippines